

DESIGN OF A METHOD FOR FORCE ANALYSIS OF A WAVE MECHANISM WITH INTERMEDIATE ROLLING BODIES

Urinov Nodir Nasilloevich

assistant

Bukhara Engineering and Technology Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10362394>

Annotation. In the article transmissions with intermediate bodies are considered rolling. A method for revealing the force static indetermination of a mechanism is presented not only using static equations, but also an additional equation that takes into account the behavior of deformations of bodies.

Keywords: engagement mechanism, torque, rolling body, rotation angle, reaction, gear ratio.

Introduction

One of the significant directions of development of modern mechanical engineering is determined in modernization etc. Designing modern machine drives. The applicability of these drives is explained by their operation in the vast majority of modern mechanical electromechanical devices. Consumer Data Properties at buildings are largely determined precisely. Technical characteristics of the mechanisms used in them. The main technical characteristics include gear ratio, efficiency, transmitted power and overall dimensions.

Particular attention should be paid to gears with intermediate bodies rolling. Transfer data is capable about ensure You With high load capacity due to multiple gearing pairs, increased torque, as well as a high gear ratio combined with relatively small dimensions [1].

Main part

The mechanism under study is a statically indeterminate system. The static indetermination of the system is determined by the need to apply not only static equations, but also additional equations that take into account the behavior of deformations of bodies [2,5]. To reveal the indetermination in the mechanism under study, we turn to a similar technique presented in [3], drawing an analogy between the lantern and epicycloidal mechanisms and, based on the results of work [4], we will solve the issue of static indetermination.

Let us assume that with the separator and profile wheel fixed, the generator, when turning due to the torque and deformations arising in the contacts of the rolling elements with the transmission elements, will rotate through a certain angle, designated as β (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Deformations when turning the generator at an angle

In the figure, the dotted line shows the initial position of the generator, and the thick solid line shows the final position after rotation. The places of deformation that occur in the rolling elements are shaded. According to the methodology for revealing the force static indetermination of the mechanism specified in the work [3], we make the assumption that the total deformation from the rolling body collapse for the second and third bodies will be determined as the dependences:

$$\delta_2 = \alpha_{K.2} \cdot \beta \quad (1)$$

$$\delta_3 = \alpha_{K.3} \cdot \beta \quad (2)$$

where: δ_2, δ_3 - total deformations of rolling elements; $\alpha_{K.2}, \alpha_{K.3}$ - lengths of normals to the line of action of forces; β - generator rotation angle.

The maximum total crushing deformation will be in the case when the normal is the maximum possible. In our case, the maximum possible shoulder is the eccentricity of the transmission.

Let us make the following assumption that those perceived by bodies rolling loads connected with responsibly with emerging deformations in contact between rolling elements and transmission elements, defined in dependencies (1, 2). Let's write down this dependence referring to [3] How:

$$\frac{P_i^\tau}{a_i^\Gamma} = \frac{P_{\max}^\tau}{a_{\max}^\Gamma} \quad (3)$$

where P_i^τ - force on the i-th rolling body; $P_{\max}^\tau$ - maximum force generated; a_i^Γ - arm of action of the force of the i-th rolling body; $a_{\max}^\Gamma$ - shoulder that occurs at maximum force.

Since the maximum possible arm of the action of forces is the eccentricity of the transmission, respectively, as noted above, we transform expression (3) to

find the force from the generator on any rolling body as:

$$P_i^\Gamma = \frac{P_{\max}^\Gamma a_i^\Gamma}{e} \quad (4)$$

gdee – transmission eccentricity.

In the designed transmission, the generator is an incoming link. The torque of the generator can be decomposed as the sum of unit moments on the rolling elements. Let's write down this dependence:

$$T_{BX} = \sum P_i^\Gamma a_i^\Gamma \quad (5)$$

Gde TVX- magnitude of the torque on the generator.

Taking into account (4) and transforming, we can write the following:

$$T_{BX} = \frac{P_{\text{бфч}}^U}{e} \sum (a_i^\Gamma)^2 \quad (6)$$

Thus, we can obtain the equation for the maximum force from the generator:

$$P_{\text{бфч}}^U = \frac{T_{BX} e}{\sum (a_i^\Gamma)^2} \quad (7)$$

In addition to the force from the generator, the rolling body in the mechanism under consideration is affected by reactions from the separator and the profile wheel. In Figure 2, a section of the transmission with a rolling body and sections of associated elements is taken separately to construct a design diagram of forces.

Rice. 2. Reactions of the rolling body from the side of the generator, separator, profile wheel.

P_g - reaction from the generator, P_k - reaction from the profile wheel, P_s - reaction from the separator, ψ - at the generator pressure on the rolling body, γ - angle of pressure of the profile wheel on the rolling body

Angle Definition ψ :

$$\psi = \arcsin\left(\frac{e}{r_2} \sin(\beta)\right) \quad (8)$$

Wherer₂ - radius of the centers of rolling bodies.

For determining V_1 enter the values of the radial and tangential components of velocity V And V_1 .

$$V_1 = -etg(\psi) \cos(\beta) - e \sin(\beta) \quad (9)$$

$$V_2 = \frac{S}{i_0} \quad (10)$$

g - transmission ratio; S - distance from the center of the generator to the circle of the centers of the rolling elements; e - transmission eccentricity; ψ - angle of generator pressure on the rolling body; β - angle of rotation of the input link.

Ratio for γ (eleven):

$$\gamma = \left| \arctg\left(\frac{V_1}{V_2}\right) \right| \quad (\text{eleven})$$

Turning to (Fig. 2) we compose a system of static equilibrium equations (12,13):

$$P_g \cos(\psi) - P_k \cos(\gamma) = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$-P_s - P_k \sin(\gamma) + P_g \sin(\psi) = 0 \quad (13)$$

Using relation (12) we express P_k (14):

$$P_k = \frac{-P_g \cos(\psi)}{\cos(\gamma)} \quad (14)$$

Putting (14) into (13) we express P_s (15):

$$P_s = P_g \frac{-\cos(\psi)\sin(\gamma) + \cos(\gamma)\sin(\psi)}{\cos(\gamma)} \quad (15)$$

Conclusion

Using Microsoft Excel software, you can determine each value of the arm hg and, by substituting in formula 4, determine the values of the generator forces from the value of the arm on the desired rolling bodies

References:

1. ErShov Yu. V. Analysis and synthesis of planetary gears K-H-V with intermediate rolling elements: dis. - SE Ershov. -M.: MSTU im. Bauman, 2007. - 242 p. ill.
2. Statically indeterminate system // Wikipedia. [2014—2014]. Update date: 05/08/2014. URL: <http://ru.wikipedia.org/?oldid=62951254> (date of access: 05/08/2014).

3. Kudryavtsev V. N., Kirdyashev Yu. N. (eds.). Planetary gears: a reference book. – 1977.
4. B.N. Kudryavtsev. Planetary gears / 2nd ed., revised. and additional – M.: Mechanical Engineering, 1966.
5. Fayzilloevich, Urinov Nasillo, and Dubrovets Lyudmila Vladimirovna. "Control of force parameters during processing diamond grinding." *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research* 3.02 (2022): 73-77.

